

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF THE EXPLOSIVE BLAST RESPONSE OF CARBON FIBRE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

A finite element (FE) modelling methodology is presented to analyse the dynamic response of carbon fibre reinforced polymer laminates when loaded by the shock wave generated by an airborne explosive blast. The FE model was created using Abaqus/Explicit 6.14 and incorporates the laminate target plate and its entire supporting structure (as used in the experimental tests). The explosive blast load was modelled using the CONWEP interaction in-built in the Abaqus/Explicit software which determines the pressure loading from a chosen equivalent TNT charge mass and stand-off distance. The FE model was validated and its numerical accuracy assessed using results obtained from experimental blast tests performed on carbon-polyester and carbon-vinyl ester laminate plates. The FE model was developed to predict the out-of-plane deformation and also the initiation and propagation of delamination cracking and ply rupture in laminates. The accuracy of the FE model is quantified by comparing numerical predictions against experimental data obtained from carbon-polyester and carbon-vinyl ester laminates subjected to near- and far-field explosive blasts. The FE model can predict the dynamic deformation of the laminates to within an accuracy of ~10%. The model can also accurately determine the location and size of delamination cracks and broken plies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced polymer laminates are used extensively in military assets, such as armoured vehicles, naval ships, submarines and aircraft, which are at risk from attack using explosive ordnance. Carbon fibre laminates are also used in civil infrastructure and transportation at risk of terrorist attack, such as buildings, bridges, rail carriages and buses. For these reasons, it is important to understand the deformation and damage caused to carbon fibre composite structures subjected to explosive blasts.

A large body of experimental research has been reported on the response of various types of laminates under explosive blast loads [1]. A variety of experimental techniques are used to evaluate the response of laminates and other types of structural materials to explosive blasts, including shock tubes, ballistic pendulum [2-4] and small, intermediate and large-scale explosion tests [5-10]. However, experimental explosive blasts for research purposes can be potentially hazardous, carry significant legal responsibilities, and are usually expensive. The development of robust computer numerical modelling in comparison is a relatively rapid and inexpensive alternative, when validated against experimental data. Other difficulties include the test results being affected by the boundary conditions and test specimen geometry [5, 11].

Modelling the blast response of laminates offers the opportunity to overcome the unavoidable limitations and problems inherent with experimental tests. Major advances in the finite element (FE) modelling of the blast response of laminates have been made in recent years, which are augmented by

the rapid development of the high speed computing technology. Several 2D and 3D FE modelling approaches have been developed to compute the dynamic deformation and damage to laminates caused by an explosive shock wave [12-14].

This paper presents a validated FE modelling methodology to analyse the deformations and strains and to predict the damage to carbon fibre reinforced polymer laminates subjected to explosive blast loading. The model includes the target plate as well as the support structures so that the real experimental conditions are closely incorporated in the numerical model. The FE model can analyse the elastic displacements and permanent deformations experienced by carbon fibre laminates under the dynamic impulse exerted by an airborne shock wave. The model can predict the initiation, growth and distribution of delamination damage and broken plies in carbon fibre laminates. The accuracy of the FE model is quantified by comparing numerical predictions against experimental data obtained for carbon-polyester and carbon-vinyl ester laminates subjected to near- and far-field explosive blasts. These laminates were selected to validate the model because of their use in naval composite structures.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Explosive blast tests were performed inside a concrete-lined steel chamber which contained viewing ports to observe the blast event and to record the deformations using high-speed photography and digital-image correlation. The tests were conducted on flat square target plates (275 x 275 mm) made of woven carbon fibre infused with liquid vinyl ester or polyester resin. The panels were held within a rigid steel window frame lined with elastomeric foam resulting in a 250 x 250 mm aperture. The laminate inside the window frame was positioned vertically approximately 1 m off the ground using a supporting frame. The explosive charge was suspended from the ceiling and was located in the same horizontal plane as the centre-point location of the target plate.

The plates were tested at increasing peak overpressures and impulses of shock waves generated by detonating spherical Type 4 plastic explosive charges (cyclotrimethylenetrinitramine). The charges were exploded using a 3.8 g RP-80 EBW electric detonator. The overpressure and impulse of the shock wave were controlled by varying the explosive charge mass and stand-off distance from the laminate test plate. The blast test conditions are given in Table 1, and were either far-field and near-field. The far-field condition occurs when the stand-off distance is greater than 10-20 times the radius of the explosive charge which results in a planar shock wave impacting the target. Comparatively, a near-field detonation involves the laminate plate being loaded by both the shock wave (which may be non-planar) and the fireball (including the hot gases and detonation products). The far- and near-field detonations are noted in Table 1.

Explosive weight (g)	Stand-off distance (m)	Peak shock wave overpressure (MPa)	Shock wave impulse (Pa.s)	Field Condition
100	1.0	0.63	109	Far-field
100	0.8	1.30	154	Far-field
100	0.6	3.36	219	Far-field
100*	0.4	10.9	353	Near-field
160*	0.4	17.0	472	Near-field

Table 1: Conditions used for the experimental explosive blast tests. The symbol * indicates the shock wave properties were calculated because they could not be precisely measured.

High-frame rate digital image correlation (DIC) using the software ARAMIS (GOM mbH) was used to measure the out-of-plane displacements and strains at the back surface of the laminate plates during blast testing. Before testing, the back surface of the plates was painted white and then randomly speckled with black dots to perform the DIC. Two Photron SA5 cameras were positioned 1.7 m behind the test plate outside of the test chamber, at an angle of 22.5° from the centre of the plate, to record the relative displacements to the speckled pattern. Following blast testing, the laminate plates were

inspected using X-ray computed tomography (CT) using a GE Phoenix v/tome/xs X-ray CT unit with a micro-focus X-ray tube. The laminates were also non-destructively inspected using through-transmission ultrasonics.

3 FINITE ELEMENT METHODOLOGY

3.1 Model Setup

The FE Model was created in Abaqus/CAE (version 6.14) and analysed using the Abaqus explicit solver. The FE model included the laminate target plate and its entire supporting structure to simulate accurately the experimental tests. A schematic of the FE model is shown in Figure 1, providing the details and locations of all the modelled components. Apart from the laminate plate and the foam lining, the responses of all the other components (which were made of steel) were elastic under the blast loads, and therefore they were modelled using a linear elastic constitutive law.

Figure 1: Schematic of explosive blast test and a close-up view of the compliant boundary condition for the test plate.

In the FE model, the blast load was calculated using the ConWep algorithm which is inbuilt in the Abaqus/Explicit (version 6.14) software. The pressure load on a selected target surface was based on the charge mass and the stand-off distance between the source point and contact surface. The ConWep algorithm assumes an exponential decay in the shock wave overpressure with increasing time expressed as [15]:

$$P(t) = P_{\max(i)} \left[1 - \frac{t-t_a}{t_+} \right] \exp \left[-\frac{a(t-t_a)}{t_+} \right] \quad (1)$$

Where $P_{\max(i)}$ is the maximum pressure of the incident shock wave, t is the time after detonation, t_a is the arrival time of the shock wave, and t_+ is the duration of the positive phase of the shock wave.

The shock wave calculated using ConWep was used as the loading boundary condition applied to the surface of the laminate plate directly facing the explosive charge. A gauge point was positioned in the centre of the plate to calculate the reflective blast pressure from the shock wave. Figure 2 shows the experimental and ConWep overpressure-time curves for the far-field blast tests. The experimentally measured and the calculated shock wave curves agreed well, although with increasing blast intensity the ConWep under-predicts the impulse of the shock wave. Accurate prediction of the shock wave for near-field explosions is a limitation of ConWep, which assumes a planar wave front

and no additional effects from the fireball or detonation products. However, at close stand-off distances the pressure transducers in the experiments are engulfed by the fireball, which would greatly affect the measurement of pressure decay.

Figure 2: Measured (solid curves) and calculated (dashed curves) reflective overpress-time profiles for the far-field tests.

The carbon fibre laminate plates were modelled as linearly elastic orthotropic materials. Areal mesh refinement identified that the converged element size to be 2 mm, which resulted in approximately 270,000 nodes and 132,000 elements across the entire target surface. Damage initiation (other than delamination) was modelled using the Hashin failure criterion applied to a cross-ply laminate (which is the same fibre orientation used for the composites in the blast experiments). The criterion assumes four damage modes; namely fibre tension, fibre compression, matrix tension and matrix compression. Delamination cracking to the laminates due to blast loading was modelled using cohesive surfaces located along the interface between each of the plies. The delamination process was modelled using a bilinear traction-separation law and a mixed-mode damage criterion for crack initiation and growth.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A comparison of the experimentally measured (solid curves) and FE predicted (dotted curves) deflection-time histories of the laminate plates at the centre-point location are presented in Figure 3. The agreements between the measured and calculated deflection profiles for the carbon-polyester and carbon-vinyl ester plates were very good for the three lowest shock wave impulse tests (109, 154 and 219 Pa.s), which are all far-field blasts. However, at the two highest impulse levels (353 and 472 Pa.s), which are both near-field blasts, the prediction of the deflection-time histories using the FE model was less accurate. The model was able to calculate with good accuracy the initial centre-point displacement of the laminate plates (up to post-detonation times of ~ 0.5 ms), after which the FE model either over- or under-predicted the centre-point displacements with significant error. At the highest shock wave impulse, the plates did not return to their near-original condition, and this was due to significant permanent deformation caused by damage. This irreversible deformation was predicted by the FE model.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Experimental measurements (solid) and numerical predictions (dashed) of the centre-point displacement-time curves for (a) carbon fibre-polyester and (b) carbon fibre-vinyl ester laminates for different blast impulse levels.

The effect of increasing shock wave impulse on the experimentally measured and numerically calculated maximum centre-point displacement values to the two laminate plates are given in Table 2. As expected, the maximum displacement experienced by the laminates increased with an increase in the impulse of the shock wave. The FE model accurately predicted (within 10%) the maximum displacements of both laminate types except for one test condition. This one discrepancy for the carbon-vinyl ester laminate tested at the highest impulse level is attributed to the FE model predicting more blast-induced damage than the amount which developed in the experimental test. This is discussed further later in the paper.

Blast Impulse (Pa.s)	Field Condition	Carbon-Polyester Laminate			Carbon-Vinyl Ester Laminate		
		Exp. (mm)	FE (mm)	$\Delta\%$	Exp. (mm)	FE (mm)	$\Delta\%$
109	Far-field	13.63	14.23	4%	12.90	14.24	10%
154	Far-field	17.28	17.56	2%	16.68	17.92	7%
219	Far-field	22.50	22.04	2%	21.10	21.77	3%
353	Near-Field	34.66	32.26	7%	30.50	32.90	7%
472	Near-Field	77.34	71.44	8%	51.67	61.97	19%

Table 2: Comparison of the experimental and numerically calculated maximum centre-point displacements. $\Delta\%$ is the percentage difference between the experimental and calculated values.

The accuracy of the FE model in predicting the dynamic deformation of the laminate plates is affected by the near/far-field blast condition. As mentioned, the FE model predicted with good accuracy the response of the laminates under far-field blast loading, which involved near planar pressure loading on the target plates. The ConWep algorithm was capable of calculating with good accuracy the peak overpressure and the impulse of the incident shock wave for far-field blast events (Figure 2). However, ConWep becomes increasingly less accurate with increasing blast intensity, particularly for the near-field condition involving a non-planar front to the shock wave. It is likely that the loss in accuracy in the calculation of the peak overpressure and impulse of the shock wave with increasing charge mass or reduced stand-off distance contributed to the reduction in numerical accuracy of the FE model, particularly for the near-field condition. An accurate prediction of the shock wave condition is essential for the reliable prediction of the deformation response of the laminates using the FE model.

Following the experimental blast tests, the laminates were inspected using scanning electron microscopy, ultrasonics and X-ray computed tomography to characterise and quantify the types and amounts of damage. Under the far-field blast condition, both the carbon-polyester and carbon-vinyl ester laminates experienced fibre-matrix interfacial cracking, matrix cracking and intra-tow cracking. The volumetric density of these different types of damage increased with the overpressure and impulse of the shock wave. Similar types of blast-induced damage to laminates have been reported in other studies [6]. The damage is caused by interlaminar and membrane stresses generated during the bending displacement of the plates. Most of the damage is expected to occur at the peak displacement, when the stresses in the plate are the highest. The FE model, which uses the Hashin failure criteria, cannot predict fibre-matrix interfacial cracking. However, the model predicts that the stresses generated within the laminates under the far-field conditions should be high enough (typically above 30 MPa) to cause interfacial damage. The model also predicted stresses that were sufficiently high to cause matrix and intra-tow cracking within both types of laminate.

Increasing the shock wave impulse eventually led to the initiation and growth of delamination cracks within the laminate plates. The percentage area of the plates which contained delamination damage was measured using ultrasonics and calculated using the FE model. The comparison between the experimental and FE results are presented in Table 3. At the low blast impulses, no delamination damage was detected using ultrasonics and likewise was not predicted using the FE model. However, experimental inspection revealed that the amount of delamination damage increased with the shock wave impulse, which was predicted well by the FE model (within $\sim 10\%$). The model also accurately predicted that the carbon-polyester laminate would experience more delamination damage compared to that experienced by the carbon-vinyl ester laminate, which occurs due to its lower mechanical and interlaminar fracture toughness, as reported in [6].

Blast impulse (Pa.s)	Carbon fibre-polyester laminate		Carbon fibre-vinyl ester laminate	
	Experimental	FE	Experimental	FE
109	0%	0%	0%	0%
154	0%	0%	0%	0%
219	11%	0%	0%	0%
353	64%	58%	25%	18%
472	100%	100%	48%	47%

Table 3: Comparison of the experimentally measured and numerically predicted delamination damage areas in the laminates caused by explosive blast loading.

The FE model was also able to predict the locations and distribution of delamination damage in the laminates plates. For example, Figure 4 compares the ultrasound images and FE-generated images of the surface of the two laminates when subjected to the same blast impulse (353 Pa.s). The blue regions in both types of image indicate the location and shape of delamination damage, whereas the other regions are free from significant delamination (although may contain fibre-matrix debonding and matrix cracking that was not readily detected using ultrasonics). The delamination cracks initiated at the plate edges and propagated towards the centre as discrete damage zones where they coalesced. This was predicted using the FE model, although the calculated shapes of the delaminated regions differed from the experiments. This was largely believed to be due to the variability of the blast load and the inaccuracy of ConWep for the near-field blasts.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Delamination damage to the (a) carbon-polyester and (b) carbon-vinyl ester laminate plates subjected to 353 Pa.s blast impulse (left – experimental and right – numerically predicted). Note the blue colour represents delamination damage.

Another type of blast-induced damage was through-thickness cracking due to rupture/tearing of the plies. The cracks initiated at the plate edges at blast impulses higher than those needed to initiate delamination cracking, and then propagated rapidly towards the centre-point. Examples of these cracks observed from the top surface of the carbon-polyester laminate after testing at the two highest blast impulses (353 and 472 Pa.s) are shown in Figure 5. Figure 5 also presents the FE predictions of the cracks, and they closely match the locations and lengths observed experimentally. This reveals that the FE model can accurately predict the initiation and growth of through-thickness cracks in the carbon fibre laminates.

Figure 5: Ply rupture to the carbon-polyester laminate plates (top-view) subjected to the blast impulses of (a) 353 Pa.s and (b) 472 Pa.s (left – experimental and right – numerically predicted). Note the blue colour in the FE images represents the regions of ply rupture.

4 CONCLUSION

A FE modelling methodology has been developed and validated to analyse the deformation and

damage to carbon fibre laminates subjected to shock waves generated by an explosive blast event. Using the calculated shock wave loading, the FE model can predict the deformation behaviour, maximum centre-point displacement and deflection-time history of the laminate targets with good accuracy (in most cases). The FE model is able to predict permanent deformation and various damage mechanisms. The model can also predict when the laminate plates are permanently deformed at high shock wave impulse levels due to blast-induced damage (e.g. delamination, ply rupture). The FE model predicts the initiation and growth of delamination damage and plate tearing caused by ply rupture. The locations and lengths of this damage can also be predicted with reasonable accuracy. The model predicted the amount of delamination cracking to both types of carbon fibre laminate to within 10%, and also provided a reasonable estimation of the location and distribution of delamination cracks. The model also predicted with good accuracy the through-thickness rupture of the carbon plies under high impulse blasts.

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